

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

D5.3b Report on the Results of the Upscaling Recommendations of the Innovative Remediation Processes and Reuse Strategies

VERSION 1.0

Acknowledgement: This project is part of the PRIMA Programme supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 1923.

Disclaimer: The content of this publication is solely responsibility of the authors and it does not represent the view of the PRIMA Foundation.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8214250](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8214250)

Project Information

Project Title	Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean		
Project Acronym	InTheMED	Grant Agreement Number	1923
Program	Horizon 2020		
Type of Action	Water RIA – Research and Innovation Action		
Start Data	March 1, 2020	Duration	36 months
Project Coordinator	Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain		
Consortium	<p>Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain</p> <p>Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung (UFZ), Germany</p> <p>Università degli Studi di Parma (UNIPR), Italy</p> <p>Boğaziçi Üniversitesi (BU), Türkiye</p> <p>Centre de Recherche et des Technologies des Eaux (CERTE), Tunisia</p> <p>Technical University of Crete (TUC), Greece</p> <p>Associação do Instituto Superior Técnico para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento (IST-ID), Portugal</p>		

Document Information

Deliverable Number	D5.3b	Deliverable Name	D5.3b Report on the results of the upscaling recommendations of the innovative remediation processes and reuse strategies	
Work Package number	WP5	Work Package Title	Innovative Remediation Strategies in the MED	
Due Date	Contractual (revised)	August, 2023	Actual	August, 2023
Version Number	1.0			
Deliverable Type	Report (R)	Dissemination Level	Public (PU)	
Authors	Hanene Akrou, Hatem Baccouche, Thuraya Mellah, Lobna Mansouri, Hanen Jarray			
Co-authors	Nadim Copty, Ali K. Saysel, Irem Daloglu, İzel Uygur (BU) George Karatzas, Ioanna Anyfanti, Anthi S. Stefanarou, Constantinos V. Chrysikopoulos (TUC) Vanessa A. Godoy, Janire Uribe-Asarta, J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández (UPV) Leonardo Azevedo, Claudia Escada (IST-ID)			
Reviewers	All			

Document History

Version	Date	Stage	Reviewed by
0	20/07/2023	Creation (CERTE Team)	Hanen Jarray
0.1	24/07/2023	Review (CERTE Team)	Hanene Akrou, Hatem Baccouche, Lobna Mansouri
0.2	25/07/2023	Modifications/Enrichment (IST-ID Team)	Leonardo Azevedo, Claudia Escada
0.3	26/07/2023	Modifications/Enrichment (UPV Team)	Vanessa A. Godoy Janire Uribe-Asarta J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández
0.4	29/07/2023	Modifications/Enrichment (TUC Team)	George Karatzas, Ioanna Anyfanti, Anthi S. Stefanarou, Constantinos V. Chrysikopoulos

0.5	31/07/2023	Modifications/Enrichment (CERTE Team)	Thuraya Mellah, Hanene Akrou, Hatem Baccouche
0.6	31/07/2023	Modifications/Enrichment (BU Team)	Nadim Copty Ali K. Saysel Irem Daloglu İzel Uygur
0.7	01/08/2023	Review/Enrichment	Hatem Baccouche, Lobna Mansouri
0.8	04/08/2023	Review/Enrichment	Thuraya Mellah, Hanene Akrou
0.9	07/08/2023	Review	Vanessa A. Godoy Janire Uribe-Asarta J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández
1.0	07/08/2023	First version	

Table of Contents

Project Information	2
Document Information.....	3
Document History	3
Table of Contents	5
List of Tables.....	7
List of Figures	7
Glossary.....	8
Executive Summary	9
1. Overview	10
2. Upscaling and Implementation of Remediation Technologies and Strategies.....	11
2.1. Grombalia Case Study, Tunisia	11
2.1.1. Upscaling Methodology	11
2.1.1.1. Statistical Approach Based on Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)	11
2.1.1.1.1. Multicriteria Decision Analysis	11
2.1.1.1.2. Estimating cumulative effects at the watershed scale	21
2.1.1.2. Synergizing with National Projects	22
2.1.2. Upscaling Recommendations in the MED Region.....	22
2.2. Konya Case Study, Türkiye	23
2.2.1. Capacity Building on Groundwater Overconsumption	23
2.2.2. Water Quality Monitoring.....	30
2.2.3. Outputs and Perspectives	34
2.3. Requena-Utiel Case Study, Spain.....	38
2.4. Tympaki Case Study, Greece	39
2.4.1. A Novel Lab Scale Methodology to Study the Interaction of Nanoparticles with Soil	39
2.4.1.1. Task 1: Modelling the Transport of Aggregating Nanoparticles in Porous Media	39
2.4.1.2. Task 2: Interaction of Titanium Dioxide with Formaldehyde in the Presence of Quartz Sand under Static and Dynamic Conditions.....	40
2.4.1.3. Task 3: Cotransport of Titanium Dioxide Nanoparticles and Formaldehyde in Saturated and Unsaturated Columns Packed with Quartz Sand	41
2.4.1.4. Task 4: Cotransport of Thiophanate Methyl and Titanium Dioxide	42

2.4.2. Upscaling at the Field Scale	42
2.5. Castro Verde Case Study, Portugal	43
3. References.....	45

List of Tables

Table 1. Pair-wise comparison scale	18
Table 2. the local and global weights of the sub-criteria.....	18
Table 3. Decision indexes	20
Table 4. Planned Modelling Activities.....	24
Table 5. Attendance to the second workshop of the living lab	25
Table 6. Day Plan	26

List of Figures

Figure 1. MCDA model	12
Figure 2. AHP decision-making tree	16
Figure 3. Land allocated to water demanding crops as drawn by the participants (on the left) and observed trefoil (blue), corn (red), and other forage crops (green) cultivated land data (on the right).....	24
Figure 4. The simple model simulated in the first workshop	27
Figure 5. Water consumption and cost estimates.....	28
Figure 6. Model Interface.....	29
Figure 7. High resolution temperature, water level and electrical monitoring data from a station in the Aksaray region.....	32
Figure 8. High resolution temperature, water level and electrical monitoring data from a station in the Çumra region.....	33
Figure 9. High resolution temperature, water level and electrical monitoring data from a station in the Karapınar region.....	34
Figure 10. Conceptual model: demand vs supply.....	35
Figure 11. Model view in Stella Architect	36
Figure 12. Sector overview	38

Glossary

AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
AWIs	Air-Water-Interfaces
CERTE	Centre de Recherches et des Technologies des Eaux
CITET	Tunis International Center for Environmental Technologies
COD	Chemical Oxygen Demand
D	Deliverable
DSS	Decision Support Systems
EC	Electrocoagulation
EF	Electro-Fenton
EOR	Electrochemical Oxidation Reduction
EP	Exploitation Plan
PBE	Population Balance Equation
GMB	Group Model Building
GW	Groundwater
KOP	Konya Plains Project Regional Development Administration
M	Milestone
MED	Mediterranean
MCDA	Multi-criteria decision analysis
NGO	Non-Governmental Organizations
SD	System Dynamics
TEMA	Turkish Foundation for Combating Soil Erosion
WP	Work Package
WSM	Weighted Sum Model

Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Türkiye.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

The overall objective of deliverable D5.3b is to establish remediation strategies that could be extrapolated to other sites in the MED region facing similar problems. Since each case study addresses a different problem, the main objective is to expand the application of remediation technologies, recommendations and strategies previously established in Subtask 5.3a. These optimised technologies and developed remediation strategies could be upscaled in other sites facing similar challenges.

Moreover, the report provides practical tools and recommendations to facilitate replication and large-scale deployment in other sites in the MED region.

1. Overview

The present deliverable presents the outputs of subtask 5.3b "Upscaling and Implementation of Remediation Technologies and Strategies" and it focuses on introducing the key recommendations for Innovative Remediation Strategies that can be upscaled and implemented in other sites facing similar challenges in the MED region.

The optimized technologies, methodologies and recommendations developed in Subtask 5.3a are provided in each case study accordingly to its specific facing challenges and problems:

- i) In Grombalia, industrial wastewater treatment,
- ii) in Konya, groundwater level declining and water quality,
- iii) in Requena-Utiel, groundwater level declining and aquifer emptying,
- iv) in Tympaki, interaction of nanoparticles with soil and saltwater intrusion, and
- v) in Castro Verde, polluting mining activities.

2. Upscaling and Implementation of Remediation Technologies and Strategies

2.1. Grombalia Case Study, Tunisia

2.1.1. Upscaling Methodology

2.1.1.1. Statistical Approach Based on Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)

Decentralized water management necessitates the implementation of sustainability management strategies that cater to the distinct characteristics of various industrial sectors. These strategies are essential in curbing industrial pollution and mitigating its adverse environmental effects. To achieve this, it is imperative to thoroughly assess the potential benefits and impacts of newly developed wastewater treatment technologies employed within industries. Specifically, their implications for groundwater and surface water must be compared against the existing practices. The overarching aim is to identify, assess and upscale the appropriate industrial practices that effectively preserve groundwater while minimizing pollution.

Given the potential for irreversible consequences brought about by global environmental change, there is an urgent need of a sustainable development transition. In this transformative process, environmental decision-making (EDM) assumes a pivotal role by providing guidance on choices that influence the environment. However, environmental decisions are intricate and often entail conflicting objectives among multiple stakeholders that cannot be simultaneously satisfied. To effectively address the complexities of environmental decision problems, which involve diverse stakeholders, objectives, and alternatives, the application of multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methods is commonly employed [1]. Therefore, a comprehensive evaluation will be carried out on three sectors: textiles, agri-food, and tanning using the Multi-criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA).

2.1.1.1.1. Multicriteria Decision Analysis

Multi-criteria decision-making typically encompasses six key steps: problem formulation, requirement identification, goal setting, alternative identification, criteria development, and the application of decision-making techniques [2, 3]. The choice of mathematical techniques

employed in this process depends on the specific characteristics of the problem at hand and the complexity involved.

In our context, the study involves creating an MCDA model based on scenarios derived from the best industrial practices aimed at reducing contamination of water resources.

The process of defining, selecting, and ranking alternatives was carried out by incorporating a combination of the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and the Weighted Sum Model (WSM) approaches as depicted in Figure 1, utilizing experts' values and preferences.

Figure 1. MCDA model

In this framework, the issue rises from the existence of established, influential, and diverse enterprises in the designated area under study. The study area hosts approximately 101 industries known for their polluting activities. These industries make a substantial impact on water management challenges, affecting both the quantity and quality of water. Their direct or indirect influence disrupts the local water cycle, with the textile, agri-food, and tanning sectors being the primary culprits behind these concerns.

- Problem identification and objectives definition

Regarding this case study, the issue stems from the pervasive existence of well-established, influential, and diversified industrial companies. The relentless expansion of these industries

has led to an increased demand for freshwater and has had a widespread impact on the quality of water resources in the region. This situation has resulted in significant challenges in water management, affecting local authorities, stakeholders, and users.

The consequences directly or indirectly disrupt the local water cycle and primarily involve the textile, agri-food, and tanning sectors.

- *Alternatives identification and assessment*

In this study, an alternative is an industrial wastewater treatment practice, which can be either an in-situ practice or a developed remediation technology.

Six specific alternatives have been identified for comprehensive assessment, and they are as follows:

Alternative 1: In-situ practice in the textile industry

Concerning the textile industry, the generated wastewaters are treated in-situ. The raw wastewater is collected in a homogenization basin, where they undergo a coagulation/flocculation treatment process. Subsequently, the treated wastewater is stored in a storage basin before being released into the sanitation network.

Alternative 2: Remediation technology for the textile industry

To improve the overall quality of treated wastewater from the textile industry, various scenarios were examined beforehand to determine the most cost-effective technology for both reuse purposes and pollution reduction.

Water samples were obtained from the homogenization basin of the textile industry, and a feed volume of 1L was continuously circulated for 3 hours through the BDD (Boron-Doped Diamond) electrodes. The electrolysis process of the wastewater samples was carried out under the galvanostatic mode.

Alternative 3: In-situ practice in the agri-food industry

Within the slaughterhouse industry, the wastewater treatment process begins with pre-treatment stages, including degreasing and grit removal, which effectively eliminate greases,

oils, floating debris, gravel, and sand. Subsequently, a physical-chemical process involving coagulation/flocculation is employed, followed by biological treatment. The resulting treated wastewater is then subjected to sedimentation for further clarification and subsequently stored for potential reuse, specifically for irrigating olive groves situated near the industry.

Alternative 4: Remediation technology for the agri-food industry

In this study, the agrifood wastewaters were obtained after undergoing an in-situ pre-treatment process within the industry. A remediation technology was implemented by sequentially combining the EOR (Electrochemical Oxidation Reduction) and EC (Electrocoagulation) processes. This technology involved a 1-hour EC process followed by a 3-hour EOR process using bipolar BDD (Boron-Doped Diamond) electrodes, which was previously described in [4].

Alternative 5: In-situ practice in the leather industry

The wastewater treatment plant implemented within the tannery under investigation. Initially, the collected raw wastewater undergoes pre-treatment using a coagulation/flocculation process. Subsequently, a first decantation process is conducted to separate the sludge from the clarified water. The recuperated water then flows through a denitrification basin, followed by an aeration step. Next, the water undergoes degassing before proceeding to the second decantation stage. Finally, the clarified water is passed through a sand filter prior to its release into the natural environment.

Alternative 6: Remediation technology for the leather industry

To remediate the recuperated tannery wastewater, a sequential remediation process involving EF (Electro-Fenton) and EC (Electrocoagulation) processes was employed. Before subjecting the wastewater to the EF and EC processes, a preliminary filtration pre-treatment was conducted using a cellulose acetate membrane filter with a pore size of 0.45 μm and a diameter of 293 mm. This pre-treatment step aimed to eliminate solid materials present in the wastewater. The electrochemical processes were powered by a direct current supply (PS500 Adamant Technologies), following the methodology outlined by Rezgui et al. [5].

- Criteria identification and AHP tree for decision making

The inclusion of criteria or indicators that influence the final decision is a critical aspect of conducting a multi-criteria analysis [6]. In this study, two primary levels of criteria were utilized to assess suitable industrial practices for groundwater preservation and pollution reduction: water resources quality management and water resources quantity management (Fig. 3). Each criterion level further encompasses multiple sub-criteria.

The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), a widely recognized multi-criteria decision-making method, was initially proposed by Thomas Saati in 1980 [7]. This decision support method relies on various parameters and criteria, which can be either quantitative or qualitative. The AHP model emulates human thinking and simplifies complex decisions by breaking them down into more manageable problems, thereby reducing their overall complexity.

Figure 2. AHP decision-making tree

The AHP follows a hierarchical structure where different levels represent primary and secondary criteria, with intermediate levels determined in relation to the overarching goal at the higher level.

A total of four indicators were gathered from various alternative indicators, primarily based on experts' consultation, according to the indicator selection criteria:

Principal criteria 1: Water resources quality management

- Sub-criteria 1: COD Removal efficiency
- Sub-criteria 2: Wastewater discharge area; sanitation network or natural network

Principal criteria 2: Water resources quantity management

- Sub-criteria 3: Groundwater supplies
- Sub-criteria 4: non-conventional water production (%)
 - Criteria weighting

Based on the decision hierarchy tree (Figure 2), the criteria were compared using pair-wise comparisons among options within the same sub-criterion or at a similar level. These comparisons were then organized into pair-wise comparison matrices. The elements that shared the same node were compared with each other based on their relative importance to the objective being considered.

The relative importance of two criteria is assessed using a numerical scale ranging from 1 to 9 (Table 1). In this scale, it is assumed that the importance of the i^{th} criterion is equal to or greater than the j^{th} criterion. Intermediate values can also be assigned within the scale.

Table 1. Pair-wise comparison scale [7]

Intensity of importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two alternatives contribute equally to the objective
2	Weak or slight	Intermediate value
3	Moderate importance	Experience and judgement slightly favour one alternative over another
4	Moderate plus	Intermediate value
5	Strong importance	Experience and judgement strongly favour one alternative over another
6	Strong plus	Intermediate value
7	Very strong	An alternative is favoured very strongly over another
8	Very, very strong	Intermediate value
9	Extreme importance	One of the alternatives is undisputedly preferred to the other one

The overall weight of each sub-criterion is calculated by multiplying the weights of all hierarchy levels. Table 2 shows the local and global weights of the sub-criteria determined using the AHP method.

Table 2. the local and global weights of the sub-criteria

Principal criteria	Local weight	Sub-criteria	Local weight	Global weight
Water resources quality management	0.50	Wastewater discharge area	0.33	0.167
		Removal efficiency	0.67	0.333
Water resources quantity management	0.50	Groundwater supplies	0.50	0.250
		Industrial water reuse	0.50	0.250

- Criteria aggregation

The Weighted Sum Complete Aggregation method (WSM) is a straightforward approach to multi-attribute utility analysis that utilizes linear relationships. It begins by standardizing the performance values across all criteria, followed by assigning relevant weights to these criteria. Next, the standardized performance values are multiplied by their respective weights, and the resulting scores are added together to calculate a weighted total score for each alternative. Finally, a ranking or weighted total score is determined, with the best alternative being the one that achieves the highest weighted sum or score. WSM's simplicity and effectiveness make it an appealing choice for decision-making processes involving multiple attributes.

The initial stage of the aggregation process involved arranging the performances of the sub criteria into a performance matrix.

To address the varying measurement scales of the problem parameters, a standardization procedure within a defined range of values is essential. In this research, the Min-Max normalization technique was chosen for this purpose. This approach proves to be particularly suitable when seeking the best operating condition, especially in cases where the score boundaries of the variable (i.e., Min and Max values) are known. By applying Min-Max normalization, the data is transformed into a common scale, enabling fair and meaningful comparisons for decision-making processes.

Given a set of values $\{f_{ij}\}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ (number of criteria), $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$ (number of alternatives), the normalized performances which vary between 0 and 1 are given by:

$$f_{ij}^* = \frac{f_{ij} - \min_{i=1, \dots, n}\{f_{ij}\}}{\max_{i=1, \dots, n}\{f_{ij}\} - \min_{i=1, \dots, n}\{f_{ij}\}} ; f_{ij}^* = \frac{\max_{i=1, \dots, n}\{f_{ij}\} - f_{ij}}{\max_{i=1, \dots, n}\{f_{ij}\} - \min_{i=1, \dots, n}\{f_{ij}\}}$$

With f_{ij}^* : *standardized performance*

To standardize the qualitative sub-criteria "Wastewater discharge area," a pair-wise comparison matrix is utilized. This matrix allows for a systematic assessment of the sub-criteria, ensuring a consistent and comparable representation.

The standardized value of each performance was multiplied by its respective global weight (w_i) as per the following equation: $R_i = \sum_1^n w_i \cdot r_{ij}$,

with:

R_j : Decision index. It varies between 0 and 1; 0 is the least suitable industrial practice and 1 is the most suitable.

w_i : Weight of sub-criterion i

r_{ij} : Standardized performance value of sub-criterion i related to site j

n : number of sub-criteria

- Decision analysis

In the context of evaluating the in-situ and the remediation industrial practises based on four sub-criteria - COD Removal efficiency, Wastewater discharge area, Groundwater supplies, and non-conventional water production (%) - a multicriteria analysis was conducted to aid the decision-making process. After analysing the data, the decision index values (Table 3) for each alternative were obtained. The best practices in textile, agrifood and in leather industries emerged as the most favourable options, boasting the highest decision index value of, respectively, 0.965, 0.875, and 0.763. This indicates superior performance compared to the in-situ alternatives and confirms the positive impact and ability of the developed remediation technologies to improve the current degraded state of the aquifer.

Meanwhile, in-situ textile and leather industries' practices had the lowest decision index value of, respectively, 0.263 and 0.305 signifying a potential pollution situation.

Table 3. Decision indexes

Alternatives	Decision index (R_i)
Textile industry	0.263
Best practice textile industry	0.965
Agrifood industry	0.425
Best practice agrifood industry	0.875
Leather industry	0.305
Best practice leather industry	0.763

To make the choice more efficient and feasible the final choice should consider stakeholders' preferences and priorities. It is essential to engage in a sensitivity analysis to gauge the robustness of the results, considering potential changes in criteria weights. By visualizing the

decision index values using charts, stakeholders can better comprehend the relative performance of each alternative and make informed decisions, aligning with the objectives of the evaluation process.

The analysis unequivocally demonstrates the significant positive impact of the developed remediation technologies and their potential to enhance the current deteriorated condition of the aquifer. Based on the results, it is evident that implementing these remediation strategies offers a promising solution to address the aquifer's degradation. Therefore, the actionable decision is to prioritize the adoption and implementation of these technologies to restore and safeguard the aquifer's health and sustainability. Additionally, ongoing monitoring and periodic evaluation of the remediation efforts are crucial to assess their effectiveness and make necessary adjustments if needed. By taking prompt and well-informed actions, it is possible to work towards preserving the aquifer's vital resources for future generations and mitigating the adverse effects of its degradation on the surrounding ecosystem and communities.

2.1.1.1.2. Estimating cumulative effects at the watershed scale

A statistical inference was performed to estimate the cumulative impact of the various designed practices on the water resources at the watershed scale. To do so, data on textile, agrifood and leather industries in the watershed were collected. The information collected shows that 56% of the industries are a textile industry, 13% are leather industries, and around 30% are agrifood industries. The information gathered provides insight into water use and the quantity of pollution generated by these sectors. As there is no accurate information on the industries water consumption, the wastewater discharge was used as a proxy of the water use. The wastewater discharged in sanitation network or rivers was about 8363 m³ per day. Considering the assumption that the industries adopt the best designed practices, it seems that the technological change affects either the industry water mass balance and the water withdrawal in absolute basis and results in water recovery that can reach 92%. The technological shift will have a substantial impact on the agrifood sector's performance. This sector has a high-water demand in comparison to the other two sectors and will produce treated effluent that will be completely reused in the watershed as water available for irrigation.

2.1.1.2. Synergizing with National Projects

The A-RESET project “Supporting Water Sector Reforms in Tunisia” is a national project launched by the Tunisian Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources, and Fisheries (MARHP) and funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ) with GIZ technical support.

On the upscaling activity, the InTheMED project has linked up with the A-RESET project, through the component “Accompanying territorial actors for an integrated approach to the sustainable management of water resources in the industrial sector, which is implemented by CITET (Tunis International Center for Environmental Technologies).

This intervention's goal is to establish a multi-actor territorial partnership and a collective dynamic that reduces the pressure that human activity is placing on the Grombalia aquifer resources. This partnership will result in an action plan that is jointly created and approved.

The InTheMED project's contribution to this dynamic is to offer technical assistance to local actors for the development of a remediation strategy, specifically in the industrial sector. This assistance is founded on the knowledge gained from the project and on best practices created at a particular sectoral level and to show how these solutions and method can be duplicated.

2.1.2. Upscaling Recommendations in the MED Region

As a result of completing subtask 5.3b, the research team has experimented an approach to codesigning a remediation strategy tailored to given case study. However, the suggested solution is a best practice that might be applied to other similar contexts confronting similar issues of sustainable groundwater management. Furthermore, the InTheMED project partners form a community of practices that should be consolidated to increase the project's impact. A structure is thus required to organize the action of this community at the Mediterranean regional level.

2.2. Konya Case Study, Türkiye

2.2.1. Capacity Building on Groundwater Overconsumption

The system dynamics (SD) approach was adopted in the living lab activities. The objectives of SD approach are understanding the underlying cause of a problematic dynamic behaviour or trend within the system, diagnosing the structural foundations of such behaviour, and identifying and testing leverage points within the system to stop or reverse the undesirable trend [8]. Based on the identified problem and the model's intended use, models created using this method concentrate on the behaviour of important variables over time and the feedback structure that generates the observed behaviour. To detect and capture significant feedback loops, appropriate stock and flow structures are constructed, and their relationships are represented with mathematical expressions.

It is mostly beneficial to involve stakeholders in practical sustainability research. To incorporate stakeholders in system dynamics research, academics introduced a concept known as Group Model Building (GMB) in the 1980s. GMB, in its broadest sense, is a collection of methods for building system dynamics models for decision-making that involve stakeholders who stand to gain or lose from the decision's outcome. Discovering the potential leverage that stakeholder participation brings to the models is the goal of GMB. The necessity for a deeper level of stakeholder participation is achieved by incorporating them directly in the model-building process, from the beginning with problem identification to the finish with policy analysis. Researchers have the option to elicit stakeholders' assumptions, ideas, knowledge, and mental models through a guided GMB study, which provides an opportunity to build a comprehensive understanding of the linkages between various system components.

The second workshop on February 17, 2022, was intended to build upon the outcomes of the first workshop of the living lab, which took place in Konya on September 30, 2021 (please refer to M4.1[9]). First a brief bulletin of the first workshop was created, outlining its intended purpose, activity structure, intellectual outputs in the form of visual objects, and the discussion on the road ahead. This was done to avoid losing contact with our key informants and stakeholders to the participatory governance analysis during the six months in between the two workshops. Individual participants received this newsletter in their native language, announcing to them that the Turkish team would like to see them again in February 2022.

The "reference modes" from the first workshop were confirmed with data along the road, and the BU team grouped the policy proposals into categories. During the second workshop, these were presented, prior to the main activities of the second workshop. Figure 3 provides an example.

Figure 3. Land allocated to water demanding crops as drawn by the participants (on the left) and observed trefoil (blue), corn (red), and other forage crops (green) cultivated land data (on the right)

To focus on specific and important issues one at a time rather than all at once, the topics raised by the participants during the first workshop were segmented, while preparing for the second workshop. For that purpose, the intended modelling efforts were created, and they are listed in Table 4.

Table 4. Planned Modelling Activities

Planned Modelling Activities			
	I (Morning)	II (Afternoon)	III (To be completed by the research team)
Groundwater Level	×	×	×
Number of Wells	×	×	×
Yield	×		
Green Plants vs Cereals Area		×	
Traditional vs Modern Irrigation			×

The aim was to discover the relationship between groundwater supply and demand in the morning, taking agricultural product yields and groundwater wells into consideration. The crop

selection was explored in the afternoon, excluding yield. The attendance to the second living lab and the day plan are presented below in Tables 5 and 6. The program is designed to first build consensus with the participants on the problem definition and basic model template. After that, the topic at hand would be thoroughly examined to improve the diagram, add new variables as needed, and uncover the connections between those variables.

Table 5. Attendance to the second workshop of the living lab

Affiliation	Title / Occupation
Alibeyhüyüğü Irrigation Cooperative	Manager
	Assistant Manager
Ankara University	Academic
Çumra Irrigation Union	Manager
	Officer
Chamber of Agriculture in Çumra DSİ	Agricultural Engineer
	Geophysics Engineers (2)
	Surface Waters Department Manager
Hydropolitics Association	Academic
Konya Commodity Exchange	Officer
Konya Plains Project Regional Development Administration (KOP)	Project Development Coordinator
	Engineer
Konya Leader Farmer Association	President
	Agricultural Engineer
	Farmers (4)
Turkish Foundation for Combating Soil Erosion (TEMA)	Officer
Total Attendance:	20

Table 6. Day Plan

Morning	09:00 AM	Greeting
	09:30 AM	Opening: Meet & Greet Recap of the first workshop
	10:00 AM	1st Session: Agreement on problem definition & model diagram
	10:30 AM	Coffee Break
	10:50 AM	2nd Session: Conceptual Model Building Model-based discussion on policy proposals
Afternoon	1:00 PM	Sample Model Simulation
	1:30 PM	3rd Session: Agreement on problem definition & model diagram
	2:00 PM	Coffee Break
	2:20 PM	4th Session: Conceptual Model Building Model-based discussion on policy proposals
	3:30 PM	Closing

The welcome and summary of the first living lab were followed by the opening session, which concentrated on creating basic causal loop diagrams. Participants were instructed by the facilitator to think of variables as stocks and flows. Modelers concurrently transferred the

whiteboard's contents into the modelling program Stella Architect and reflected them on the large projection screen as the debate was being led by the facilitator, who also translated what was being spoken to the whiteboard. Following that, just like in the previous workshop, a simple simulation model was created on Stella Architect to acquaint newcomers with the software and to refresh the memory of returning participants (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The simple model simulated in the first workshop

The second session started with the following questions and focused on these topics: "what causes an increase in groundwater levels?" and "what causes a decline in the number of active wells?". The procedure was interrupted by the arguments and miscommunications in the group. There was a discussion on well pumps, their power, and well flow rates, following the discussion on the capacity of the groundwater supply. The plenary dispersed for the lunch break after the session ended with a commitment to tackling the "demand side" of the issue in the afternoon, which was anticipated to shed more light on the factors that influence shifting groundwater demand.

In the final session of the day, it was examined the policy proposal about crop choice and arrived at the conclusion that crop rotation strategies would be a better policy proposal for the overall benefit of the nation and in terms of groundwater demand than abandoning particular crops.

After that, the expansion in irrigated land and the factors that led to it were explored. Issues related to water quality were briefly discussed.

The third workshop focused on model-based policy design and was conducted in Konya city centre. This workshop followed the fieldwork on model validation conducted in January 2023, consisting of six visits in three days, interviewing 19 people on model structure and behaviour. 28 people joined the workshop, 15 of them following the living lab since its inception in Fall 2021. The day was organized around the first two problem layers of the second workshop (M4.2 [10]) exploring the impact of “irrigated crop yield targets” and “irrigated cropland targets” on key performance measures. Workshop opened with a progress presentation of the project team (20 min), emphasizing modelling and validation of both the system dynamics and the hydrological models and continued with four breakout groups of seven people.

In the morning session, four breakout groups were designed with respect to their professional interests. Farmers, water authority, academics and agricultural authorities built four breakout groups of almost equal size. The first session was 40 minutes focusing on the first problem. To observe possible water consumption corresponding to yield targets and to calculate water costs corresponding to assumed depth, the exercise was supported with graphical illustrations in Figure 5. With this information, the group iteratively worked out target yields for the three crops (winter cereals, summer cereal and sugar beets). After a break, they simulated their decision on the model, available to them through the model interface.

Figure 5. Water consumption and cost estimates

While the feedback-rich model developed after the second workshop (M4.2 [10]) documented by D4.2 [11] simulated target yields through factor adjustment and goal setting loops, the version underlying the interface in Figure 6 is a relatively simplified version of it, where the

yield targets are exogenous and constant over the next 20 years. In the third session (30 min) the breakout groups presented their observations to the plenary. The boom and decline in number of wells caused by declining water levels, corresponding shift towards rainfed agriculture were notable observations and subject of plenary debate. The behaviour patterns were quite robust to different yield targets. Simulator also allowed the participants to play with the supply side measure of “surface water supply” and technology side measure of “irrigation efficiency” as agreed during the first workshop. They also tested the unpopular measures of quotas for the number of wells and the sugar beet cultivation. Quotas for the number wells, in some simulations, leading to larger basin wide (public) profits was another notable observation.

Figure 6. Model Interface

The afternoon sessions were a replica of the first three sessions, this time answering the question of “target cropland”, with an identical calculation phase followed by breakout group simulations and plenary presentations. Since the crop profit exercises were already done during the morning, the 4th session immediately started with the same breakout groups, this time simulating their target crop lands, rather than target crop yield. This also changed the scale of the activity from farm level to basin level, because while yield targets were a farm level decision, crop land cover target was a broader planning decision. Model was a simplified version of the feedback-rich

model in D4.3 [12], this time, the logit model of crop/land choice was substituted with breakout decisions. The simulator interface was identical except the “goal setting” quadrant input variables.

During the closing session, facilitators highlighted some surprises that appeared during the simulation exercises. These can be summarized as:

- a. The favourite supply line solution, inter-basin surface water transfers are not significantly affecting the sustainability of the groundwater resources; neither it creates a significant economic contribution.
- b. If relatively open /free access to groundwater infrastructure (well drilling) continues, it is likely that the number of operating wells will start declining soon as the groundwater level declines, and its extractions become costly.
- c. Apparently unpopular demand side policies, ex. incentives for less water demanding crops, quotas on irrigated crops, metering to reduce water consumption per land etc. are to the benefit of the region-scale agricultural economy. This is emphasizing the tragedy of the commons nature of the problem and highlighting the need for cooperation and coordination to reduce water consumption.

It was noted in the workshops that soil salinization is becoming a serious problem in some parts of the basin. However, water scarcity remains the most pressing issue.

It was also noted that there are plans to upgrade the Konya wastewater treatment plant to improve effluent water quality to allow its reuse in irrigation. However, this appears to be a long-term plan as the upgrading of the wastewater treatment plant may take some years to complete. Moreover, Turkish regulations should be changed to allow for the use of treated wastewater for irrigation purposes. Currently, treated wastewater is allowed for use in public areas such as parks.

A fully detailed report on the workshop is provided in M4.2 [10] and M4.4 [13].

2.2.2. Water Quality Monitoring

As part of the efforts to upgrade groundwater monitoring in the Konya Closed Plain, a network of high-resolution monitoring wells was installed in 2019 by the State Hydraulic Works (Devlet

Su İşleri, DSI). The network consisted of 122 DCX-22 series sensors manufactured by Keller Inc., which allow for the measuring of temperature, water level and electrical conductivity. The sensors were set to provide measurements of these three parameters at about 10-minute time interval. Further details of the high-resolution monitoring at the Konya Closed plain is presented in Deliverable 2.4: “Reinforcement of The Systematic Monitoring and Data Sharing in The MED Region”.

Sample plots of the temperature, water level and electrical conductivity at three monitoring locations are given below (*Figure 7-9*). The monitoring stations are located in the east (Aksaray), south (Çumra) and central (Karapınar) regions of the basin respectively.

It is also observed that during the high groundwater extraction periods, the data show an increase in the electrical conductivity and temperature. While temperature variations are small, the electrical conductivity (salinity) increases tend to be large with possible impacts on crop yields.

The high-resolution monitoring station would enable real-time data collection, providing valuable insights into groundwater fluctuations, helping authorities to identify potential risks of overexploitation and take timely mitigation measures. The installation of a cluster of sensors over a large area such as the Konya closed basin, can provide water authorities with an overview of water quality and quantity measures which can help in the identification of local hotspots and devise strategies to limit their impacts.

Figure 7. High resolution temperature, water level and electrical monitoring data from a station in the Aksaray

Figure 8. High resolution temperature, water level and electrical monitoring data from a station in the Çumra region

Figure 9. High resolution temperature, water level and electrical monitoring data from a station in the Karapinar region

2.2.3. Outputs and Perspectives

During the second modelling workshop, a seed model was created together with the participants as described in detail in Deliverable 4.2 [11]. Since then, we, as the modelling team, have been developing the seed model to eliminate those limitations.

The seed model assumed a single crop, and a constant target yield which drives the groundwater consumption. Different crop types and relative attractiveness of crops were added, driven by their profitability, to incorporate the crop pattern change in the study area,

and built a goal setting structure in the model to endogenize the potential changes in target yield.

A groundwater model to calibrate with the hydrogeological model developed for the basin was also developed. In the seed model, the groundwater stock had a volumetric unit; while in the model under development, it was converted to the hydraulic head, with a unit in length. The lateral movement of groundwater is formulated according to Darcy’s Law, and conversions from water volume to water head (and vice versa) are formulated accordingly when necessary.

Figure 10 shows the conceptual model. The groundwater demand side involves crop choice (land allocated for each crop), factor consumption (irrigation), yield goal setting, and crop production. Supply side involves groundwater and groundwater infrastructure, i.e., wells and pumps. While the demand for groundwater is driven by the land use (crop pattern) and targeted yield, its consumption is limited by the availability of groundwater, the cost of groundwater extraction, and the capacity of existing infrastructure.

Figure 10. Conceptual model: demand vs supply

The model runs on a yearly basis, from 2000 to 2050. Figure 11 shows the model, as built on Stella Architect. It focuses on groundwater, wells (infrastructure for groundwater supply), crop choice, and factor consumption (irrigation) and yield dynamics.

Figure 11. Model view in Stella Architect

Figure 12 is a schematic representation of the model sectors and shows the interaction (input/output relationships) between different parts of the model. Blue arrows introduce exogenous variables, which can be used to test different environmental scenarios (such as climate) and policy options (such as crop prices, quotas on crops, restrictions on groundwater extraction infrastructure etc.). Orange arrows show endogenous interactions between sectors of the model. Sectors' colours indicate their place in the conceptual model (Figure 10): grey sectors belong to the demand side and yellow sectors belong in the supply side. Production factor consumption and yield goal setting sector has both supply and demand side variables and contain feedback relationships between the two sides. Groundwater and groundwater infrastructure sector determines the water availability and accessibility, i.e., yearly groundwater extraction capacity. Factor adjustment and goal setting sector determines target yield for each crop type and adjusts the desired irrigation level accordingly. Desired irrigation water is determined from the desired irrigation level and how much land is allocated to each crop. Groundwater extraction depends both on the extraction capacity, and the demand for groundwater. Obtained (actual) yield for each crop type is calculated based on the realized irrigation level. Revenue from obtained yield and groundwater extraction cost determine the profitability and the attractiveness of crops. Farmers' land use choice depends on relative attractiveness of crops; more land is allocated to a crop with relatively high attractiveness, and vice versa.

Further Details about the SD model, including the equations used and its calibration are presented in D4.3 [14].

Figure 12. Sector overview

2.3. Requena-Utiel Case Study, Spain

In the Spanish study case, over the past two decades, the aquifer has been exploited, leading to a progressive decrease in water levels and a negative aquifer storage balance, indicating depletion. The Hydrological Plans of the Júcar Water Authority for the 2015-2021 [15] and 2021-2027 [16] terms state that the Requena-Utiel groundwater mass is in a bad quantitative state and outline remediation strategies. A significant step was taken in December 2016 with the creation of the Exploitation Plan (EP) for the Requena-Utiel groundwater mass [17], aiming for efficient management and planning to ensure reliable service for users and restore the good quantitative status of the groundwater mass. While the plan has shown positive preliminary results, such as increased or stabilized levels in some piezometers, it appears that relying solely on the Exploitation Plan as a remediation strategy may not be sufficient. In Deliverable D5.3a [18], in conjunction with the Exploitation Plan, a dual approach was recommended, involving both the simultaneous use of an innovative and accessible tool for monitoring the aquifer state and the implementation of a strategy to restore water levels.

Indeed, the dual approach, originally proposed for the Requena-Utiel aquifer case study, can be extended to the broader context of the MED Region. By utilizing climatic data and models, groundwater usage, and monitoring data of groundwater levels (as demonstrated in Deliverables D2.2 [19] and D2.3[20]), it is feasible to develop an innovative and accessible smart

model for the MED Region, either in another aquifer with a similar problem or even on a regional scale. This model can then be integrated into a Decision Support System (as shown in Deliverables D6.1 [21] and D6.2 [22]), making it available for all stakeholders involved in groundwater management.

Additionally, the implementation of the water balance approach with uncertainty consideration, which was developed at the Kansas Geological Survey [23-24], is entirely feasible in the MED Region, if the specified indications for the method are adhered to. This approach can serve as a valuable management tool not only for depleted aquifers but also for preventing depletion. The method's requirements, as discussed in Deliverable 5.3a [18], involve the annual pumping and the average water level change. By meeting these criteria, the method can effectively contribute to sustainable groundwater management in the MED Region.

Upscaling the approaches to the MED region does not require significant changes in the methods; rather, it primarily involves utilizing the dataset accurately in both space and time scales. However, the main limitation of the proposed dual approach lies in the lack of data on groundwater pumping and monitoring.

2.4. Tympaki Case Study, Greece

2.4.1. A Novel Lab Scale Methodology to Study the Interaction of Nanoparticles with Soil

A novel methodology and model were developed at the TUC to study the migration and aggregation of nanoparticles in porous media. Specifically, the following four tasks were performed:

2.4.1.1. Task 1: Modelling the Transport of Aggregating Nanoparticles in Porous Media

A novel mathematical model was developed to describe the transport of nanoparticles in water saturated, homogeneous porous media with uniform flow. The model accounts for the simultaneous migration and aggregation of nanoparticles. The nanoparticles are assumed to be found suspended in the aqueous phase or attached reversibly or irreversibly onto the solid matrix. The Derjaguin-Landau-Verwey-Overbeek theory was used to account for possible repulsive interactions between aggregates. Nanoparticle aggregation was represented by the

Smoluchowski population balance equation (PBE). Both reaction-limited aggregation and diffusion-limited aggregation were considered. Particle-size dependent dispersivity was accounted for. In order to overcome the substantial difficulties introduced by the PBE, the governing coupled partial differential equations were solved by employing adaptive operator splitting methods, which decoupled the reactive transport and aggregation into distinct physical processes. The results from various model simulations showed that the transport of nanoparticles in porous media is substantially different than the transport of conventional biocolloids. In particular, aggregation was shown to either decrease or increase nanoparticle attachment onto the solid matrix, depending on particle size, and to yield early or late breakthrough, respectively. Finally, useful conclusions were drawn regarding possible erroneous results generated when aggregation, particle-size dependent dispersivity or nanoparticle surface charges are neglected. This work has been published in the journal: *Water Resources Research* [25].

2.4.1.2. Task 2: Interaction of Titanium Dioxide with Formaldehyde in the Presence of Quartz Sand under Static and Dynamic Conditions

Among the most frequently occurring toxic organic substances in water is formaldehyde (FA), because of its extensive use in numerous applications by various industries including textile, furniture, aquaculture, agriculture, tannery, petrochemical, and cosmetics. Also, nanotechnology research has increased in the recent years and many revolutionary developments have taken place in this field. Titanium dioxide (TiO_2) is a nanomaterial, which has been used extensively in various commercial applications and catalytic reactions due to its very good physical, optical, electrical, and stable structural properties. TiO_2 is the 4th most abundant metal in the world, and can be found in various minerals, mainly in rutile, brocrite, anatase, but also in the human body, ash, and plants. It should be noted that TiO_2 is present in various widely used products such as paints, paper, plastics, cosmetics, food and much more. Given that both FA and TiO_2 are frequently released into the environment, they can easily infiltrate subsurface formations. Consequently, it is worthwhile to study the interaction between FA and TiO_2 in the presence of a common rock-forming mineral such as quartz sand.

The sorption of FA onto TiO_2 nanoparticles in the absence and presence of quartz sand under static and dynamic conditions, at 25 °C was investigated. The experimental results from this

work suggested that FA sorption was faster and more pronounced in the presence of quartz sand. Typical pH and ionic strength variations did not significantly affect the FA sorption process. The experimental data were satisfactorily fitted by the pseudo-second order model, indicating that the sorption mechanism was chemisorption. The experiments were conducted with clean quartz sand. The interaction of FA with quartz sand could be somewhat different if the quartz sand was not cleaned or if natural soil had been used. Assuming that FA could be relatively mobile in natural soil and sediments and could potentially contaminate the aquatic environment with numerous adverse effects on living organisms and to human health, its removal is essential. The present study suggested that combination of the sorbents TiO_2 and quartz sand can effectively remove FA from aqueous solutions. This study was published in the journal Water [26].

2.4.1.3. Task 3: Cotransport of Titanium Dioxide Nanoparticles and Formaldehyde in Saturated and Unsaturated Columns Packed with Quartz Sand

The cotransport of titanium dioxide (TiO_2) nanoparticles and formaldehyde (FA) in saturated and unsaturated porous media was investigated. The cotransport of TiO_2 nanoparticles and FA in bench scale columns packed with quartz sand was explored experimentally. The impact of air-water-interfaces (AWIs) on the cotransport of TiO_2 nanoparticles and FA in unsaturated porous media was investigated under different flow conditions and different solution ionic strengths. It was shown that substantial retention of TiO_2 nanoparticles could occur under both saturated and unsaturated conditions. It was observed that the majority of TiO_2 nanoparticles were either retained by the quartz sand surfaces or by the gas/water interfaces. The solution ionic strength significantly affected the retention of TiO_2 nanoparticles within the porous medium, an observation which is consistent with zeta potential measurements and the traditional DLVO theory. Higher ionic strengths led to nanoparticle aggregation, which in turn yielded TiO_2 retention in the column. The TiO_2 mass recovered was shown to increase with increasing flow rate in water saturated columns, but no clear trend was observed for the unsaturated columns. The observed FA retention during TiO_2 and FA cotransport experiments in both saturated and unsaturated columns was attributed to FA sorption onto TiO_2 nanoparticles, which subsequently were attached onto quartz sand. Although the DLVO theory predicted a high energy barrier for the interaction pair TiO_2 -AWI in the presence of NaCl, the experimental results did not exhibit the anticipated reduction in particle attachment, possibly

due to other retention mechanisms which are not accounted by the DLVO theory. Understanding the transport of TiO₂ nanoparticles and FA in porous media is helpful for the prediction of their migration behaviour in soil and groundwater systems, thus minimizing their hazardous impacts. This study was published in the *Vadose Zone Journal* [27].

2.4.1.4. Task 4: Cotransport of Thiophanate Methyl and Titanium Dioxide

Thiophanate methyl a common fungicide, which is used widely to control fungal diseases on crops. It has a low aqueous solubility, low volatility and tends not to be persistent in soil or water systems. It has a low mammalian toxicity; however, it is an irritant, a skin sensitizer and may also be mutagen. It should be noted that thiophanate methyl is an approved EU fungicide. Given that both thiophanate methyl and TiO₂ are frequently released into the environment, a series of transport experiments with titanium dioxide and a series of co-transport experiments with titanium dioxide and thiophanate methyl under various ionic strength and pH conditions have been performed. The experimental results suggested that increasing the solution pH: (i) reduced the sorption rate of TM onto the solid matrix, (ii) reduced the attachment rate of TiO₂ nanoparticles onto the solid matrix, (iii) increased the sorption rate of TM onto TiO₂ nanoparticles, and (iv) increased the mass recovery of both TM and TiO₂. On the contrary, increasing the ionic strength yielded: (i) increased sorption of TM onto the solid matrix, (ii) increased attachment rate of TiO₂ particles onto the solid matrix, and (iii) reduced mass recovery of both TiO₂ particles and TM solutes. Therefore, TiO₂ nanoparticles can be used to enhance the removal of TM from soil. Also, it shown that the solution pH and ionic strength can affect the TM transport characteristics with the latter one having more profound effects in the presence of TiO₂ nanoparticles. This study was published in the in the journal *Water* [28].

2.4.2. Upscaling at the Feld Scale

The methodology proposed for the mitigation of saltwater intrusion is to find the optimum pumping scheme by finding the maximum pumping rates subjected to a specific value for the groundwater level. This value is selected so that the groundwater is upgraded to a level that can ameliorate the saltwater intrusion through hydraulic control. The optimization methodology is explicitly presented in the report for D6.1 [21]. This methodology is based on the numerical simulation model of the aquifer. Thus, it is applied from the beginning to the real scale that is defined by the study site area. Therefore, an upscaling methodology is not

applicable for this approach. However, the approach is replicable and can be applied to other aquifers in the Mediterranean region aiming to mitigate not only saltwater intrusion, but groundwater level degradation in general.

Regarding the role of nanoparticles in the saturated and unsaturated zone, the novel laboratory-scale method described above is pioneering work that can be applied not only in the Tympaki aquifer but also on a national and international field scale. The present study needs further work at the laboratory scale before it can be applied at the field scale, since not much research has been done in the field of nanoparticle interaction with soils. Field data were not available for the Tympaki aquifer to improve the proposed methodology, but the validity of the methodology was confirmed by publications in well-known international journals.

2.5. Castro Verde Case Study, Portugal

The Portuguese case study is located within a mining concession. The Neves-Corvo polymetallic base metal deposit is part of the world-class Iberian Pyrite Belt of southern Portugal and Spain. The mine is situated in the southern region of Portugal, in the Alentejo province, about 15 km southeast of Castro Verde town.

Neves-Corvo mine has been developed as an underground operation, with exploitation in five major polymetallic sulphide orebodies [29]. Within the mine premises, the groundwater is a significant aquifer that connects to water supplies and a significant river that passes close to the mine [30].

The aquifer is threatened by the mining activities, ore processing and the large-scale tailing infrastructure. To mitigate risks there the mining company has a large network of control wells, some with daily readings of the water table and chemical elements indicators of contamination. However, the existing groundwater monitoring network of boreholes is spatially sparse when compared with the full extent of the mining site and therefore unable to capture all the natural, and induced, variability of the groundwater system.

At the beginning of the project the operator was building a numerical hydrogeological model based on a priori geological knowledge, the borehole data, and a set of two-dimensional electrical resistivity sections. The results produced under the geostatistical inversion of these

data allowed to complement the sparsely distributed borehole data to better constrain the model.

The results obtained under the InTheMED project illustrate the benefits of geophysical data to imaging and modelling geological subsurface properties in high-resolution. If these data can be acquired, processed, and interpreted at different periods (i.e., time-lapse geophysical data) it has the potential to depict the variations of the groundwater properties due to the mining operation activities.

3. References

- [1] Toth, W, Vacik, H. (2018). A comprehensive uncertainty analysis of the analytic hierarchy process methodology applied in the context of environmental decision making. *J Multi-Crit Decis Anal.* 2018; 25: 142– 161. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mcda.1648>
- [2] Sabaei, D., Erkoyuncu, J., & Roy, R. (2015). A review of multi-criteria decision making methods for enhanced maintenance delivery. *Procedia CIRP*, 37, 30–35.
- [3] Hirushie Karunathilake, Ezzeddin Bakhtavar, Gyan Chhipi-Shrestha, Haroon R. Mian, Kasun Hewage, Rehan Sadiq, Chapter Seven (2020). Decision making for risk management: A multi-criteria perspective, Editor(s): Faisal I. Khan, Paul R. Amyotte, *Methods in Chemical Process Safety*, Elsevier, Volume 4, 2020, Pages 239-287, ISSN 2468-6514, ISBN 9780128218242, <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.mcps.2020.02.004>.
- [4] Mouna Ghazouani, Hanene Akrou, Salah Jellali, Latifa Bousselmi (2019). Comparative study of electrochemical hybrid systems for the treatment of real wastewaters from agri-food activities, *Science of The Total Environment*, Volume 647, 2019, Pages 1651-1664, ISSN 0048-9697, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.08.023>.
- [5] Soumaya Rezgui, Mouna Ghazouani, Latifa Bousselmi, Hanene Akrou. (2022). Efficient treatment for tannery wastewater through sequential electro-Fenton and electrocoagulation processes, *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, Volume 10, Issue 3, 2022, 107424, ISSN 2213-3437, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.107424>.
- [6] Vincke, P. (1992). *Multicriteria decision-aid*. Bruxelles, Belgium: Wiley.
- [7] Saaty TL (1988) What is the analytic hierarchy process? *Mathematical models for decision support*. Springer, pp 109–121
- [8] Stave, K. (2010). Participatory system dynamics modeling for sustainable environmental management: Observations from four cases. *Sustainability*, 2(9), 2762–2784. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su2092762>

- [9] Saysel, A.k., Daloğlu Çetinkaya, I., Uygur, I., & Copty, N. (2021). InTheMED M4.1. First Living Lab Guiding Problem Identification and System Characterization (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5743792>
- [10] Saysel, A.k., Daloğlu Çetinkaya, I., Uygur, I., & Copty, N. (2022). InTheMED M4.2 Second Living Lab Scrutinizing and Refining the Conceptual Model (Version 1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6303541>
- [11] Saysel, Ali Kerem, Daloglu Cetinkaya, Irem, Copty, Nadim, & Uygur, Izel. (2022). InTheMED D4.2 Report on the Participatory Systems Mapping and the Conceptual Model (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6401942>
- [12] Saysel, Ali Kerem, Daloğlu Çetinkaya, İrem, Uygur, İzel, & Copty, Nadim. (2022). D4.3 Report on the Numeric Simulation Model Including Model Input Files (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7371405>.
- [13] Saysel, Ali Kerem, Daloğlu Çetinkaya, İrem, Uygur, İzel, & Copty, Nadim. (2023). InTheMED M4.4 Third Living Lab for Building Simulation-Based Scenario Analyses and Policy Design (Version 1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199840>.
- [14] Saysel, Ali Kerem, Daloğlu Çetinkaya, İrem, Uygur, İzel, & Copty, Nadim. (2022). D4.3 Report on the Numeric Simulation Model Including Model Input Files (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7371405>
- [15] CHJ (2015). Plan Hidrológico de la Demarcación Hidrográfica del Júcar. Ciclo de planificación hidrológica 2015-2021. Valencia. Retrieved from <https://www.chj.es/es-es/medioambiente/planificacionhidrologica/Paginas/PHC-2015-2021-Plan-Hidrologico-cuenca.aspx>
- [16] CHJ (2022). Plan Hidrológico de la Demarcación Hidrográfica del Júcar. Ciclo de planificación hidrológica 2021-2027. Valencia. Retrieved from: <https://www.chj.es/es-es/medioambiente/planificacionhidrologica/Paginas/PHC-2021-2027-Indice.aspx>
- [17] CHJ (2016). Plan de explotación de la masa de agua subterránea Requena-Utiel. Valencia. Retrieved from:

[https://www.chj.es/eses/medioambiente/PlanExplotacion/Documents/PlanExplotacion_RequenaUtiel_33_web .pdf](https://www.chj.es/eses/medioambiente/PlanExplotacion/Documents/PlanExplotacion_RequenaUtiel_33_web.pdf)

- [18] Akrou, Hanene, Mellah, Thuraya, Baccouche, Hatem, Mansouri, Lobna, Ghrabi, Ahmed, Anyfanti, Ioanna, Karatzas, George, A. Godoy, Vanessa, Uribe-Asarta, Janire, Gómez-Hernández, J. Jaime, Azevedo, Leonardo, Escada, Cláudia, Saysel, Ali Kerem, Daloglu Çetinkaya, Irem, Uygur, İzel, & Copty, Nadim. (2023). InTheMED D5.3a Report on the Appropriate Innovative Remediation Process Developed (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661080>
- [19] Chavez Garica Silva, Rafael, & Jomaa, Seifeddine. (2022). InTheMED D2.2 Report on the Existing Historical Groundwater Data in the MED Region (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7014621>
- [20] Chavez, Rafael, & Jomaa, Seifeddine. (2023). InTheMED D2.3 Report on Regional Groundwater Trends and Their Controlling Factors (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199743>
- [21] Varouchakis Emmanouil, Lyronis Antonis, Anyfanti Ioanna, & Diakoparaskevas Paraskevas. (2022). InTheMED D6.1 Report on the Development of the Innovative DSS Tool (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6304566>
- [22] Varouchakis, Emmanouil, & Anyfanti, Ioanna. (2023). InTheMED D6.2 Report on the Results of the DSS for the Case Study Sites (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7684115>
- [23] Butler, J.J., Jr., D.O. Whittemore, B.B. Wilson., & G.C. Bohling. (2016). A new approach for assessing the future of aquifers supporting irrigated agriculture, Geophysical Research Letters, v. 43, no. 5, pp. 2004-2010, doi: 10.1002/2016GL067879, 2016.
- [24] Butler, J.J., Jr., G.C. Bohling, D.O. Whittemore, & B.B. Wilson. (2020). Charting pathways towards sustainability for aquifers supporting irrigated agriculture, Water Resour. Res., v. 56, no. 10, doi: 10.1029/2020WR027961, 2020.

- [25] Katzourakis, V.E., and C.V. Chrysikopoulos (2021). Modeling the transport of aggregating nanoparticles in porous media, *Water Resources Research*, 57(1), e2020WR027946, doi:10.1029/2020WR027946
- [26] Stefanarou, A.S., and C.V. Chrysikopoulos (2021). Interaction of titanium dioxide with formaldehyde in the presence of quartz sand under static and dynamic conditions, *Water*, 13(10), 1420, doi:10.3390/w13101420, 2021)
- [27] Chrysikopoulos, C.V., and T.V. Fountouli (2023). Cotransport of titanium dioxide nanoparticles and formaldehyde in saturated and unsaturated columns packed with quartz sand, *Vadose Zone Journal*, 22, e20175, doi:10.1002/vzj2.20175
- [28] Stefanarou, A.S., V.E. Katzourakis, F. Fu, A.A. Malandrakis, and C.V. Chrysikopoulos (2023). Transport of thiophanate methyl in porous media in the presence of titanium dioxide nanoparticles, *Water*, 15(7), 1415, doi:10.3390/w13101420
- [29] Lundin Mining (2017). NI 43-101 Technical Report for the Neves-Corvo Mine, Portugal. Retrieved from: <https://lundinmining.com/operations/neves-corvo/>
- [30] Lundin Mining (2013). Technical Report for Neves-Corvo Mine and Semblana Deposit, Portugal. Retrieved from: https://www.miningdataonline.com/reports/Neves-Corvo_2013_TR.pdf